

D4.2 Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions

WP 4 Creation of Innovative Social Actions

BCNecologia

Public Report – M28

REVIEWER	DATE	VERSION
BCN	19112018	V1
NTUA, ZAB, MOBA, BCN	26112018	V2
BCN	09012019	V3

Table of contents:

1	Introduction	1
2	General description of the ICT based tools.....	1
2.1	Description of the ICT based tools	1
2.2	Main characteristics of the Social Action Plan	1
2.2.1	Integration of IT tools.....	1
2.2.2	Success factors to achieve high separate collection rates. Interaction with SA Plan 2	
3	Definition of Target Groups for the Social Actions	5
4	Methodology to define the integration of the ICT based tools	7
5	Integration of ICT tools in Zamudio’s Social Action Plan.....	3
5.1	Matrix	4
5.2	Social actions and use of ICT based tools.....	5
6	Integration of ICT tools in Halandri’s Social Action Plan	12
6.1	Matrix	13
6.2	Social actions and use of ICT based tools.....	14
7	Integration of ICT tools in Seveso’s Social Action Plan.....	18
7.1	Matrix	19
7.2	Social Actions and integration of ICT tools.....	20
8	Integration of ICT tools in Cascais’s Social Action Plan	24
8.1	Matrix	25
8.2	Social Actions and integration of ICT tools.....	26
9	Calendar of use of ICT based educational tools in the Social action Plan.....	31
10	Monitoring and expected results	36
11	Documental updating.....	37
12	Annexes	38
12.1	Update of the SA Plan	38

12.2 Reviewers comments43

Tables and figures:

Table 1	Description of ICT based educational tools.....	5
Fig. 1.	Social Action Plan scheme	1
Fig. 2.	Integration of different tools to achieve results. “Jigsaw” simile.	2
Fig. 3.	Utilities of USER identification	3
Fig. 4.	Patterns information for awareness raising purposes.....	3
Fig. 5.	Image of the Citizens App design proposal	4
Fig. 6.	Economical tools	4
Table 2	Target group and availability forecast.....	6
Table 3	Template to describe the use of the ICT based tool in the Social Action Plan.	8
Table 4	Matrix with Social Actions per pilot and ICT based educational tools (R5-R12)	2
Fig. 7.	Matrix Social Actions vs ICT tools (R5-R12) in Zamudio.....	4
Fig. 8.	Matrix Social Actions vs ICT tools (R5-R12) in Halandri	13
Fig. 9.	Matrix Social Actions vs ICT tools (R5-R12) in Seveso.....	19
Fig. 10.	Matrix Social Actions vs ICT tools (R5-R12) in Cascais	25
Table 5	Guide of Ecosolutions ID, name and availability forecast	31
Fig. 11.	Calendar for Zamudio’s Social Action Plan.....	32
Fig. 12.	Calendar for Seveso’s Social Action Plan.....	33
Fig. 13.	Calendar for Halandri’s Social Action Plan	34
Fig. 14.	Calendar for Cascais Social Action Plan.....	35
Table 6	Some of the questions provided by the pilots to be answered by the use of the ecosolutions	36
Table 7	Pilots Social Actions.....	42

Acronyms:

AR Augmented Reality

DtD Door to Door

DP Digital Project

ICT Informative Communication Technology

ID IDentification number

MG Mobile Game

MSW Municipalrban Solid Waste

PAYT Pay As You Throw

SA Social Action

QR Quick Response code

1 Introduction

One of the objectives of Waste4Think is to develop best environmental education and awareness strategies and to present it along with the implementation of all the required actions to undertake the demonstrative objectives of the Pilots sites. The final goal is to reach a high rate of empowerment and awareness and finally, a change in consumption and waste management habits among the different stakeholders involved in the implementation of the different actions. The new ICT based tools developed in the framework of Waste4Think will help to better communicate and interact with these stakeholders, increasing flexibility, transparency and better content of the awareness and empowerment actions. At the same time, these tools will help the managers of the Social Actions to have a better understanding of the knowledge and habits patterns of the users, allowing the possibility of adapting contents, messages and new interactions with the stakeholders in order to improve results. The final objective is to increase the impact of the social actions and to foster mutual learning, as well as to identify hotspots which allow to define ad hoc campaigns.

D4.2 includes only the description of the use of the IT tools (R1-R15, but specially those ones specially developed for this purpose, as learning materials, apps and serious games) to some of the strategies developed by the pilots. In this sense, only the integration of the ICT based educational tools to the environmental education strategies are explained. The full descriptions of the Environmental Educational Plan with the strategies that are already being implemented in each pilot, target groups definition, key messages, etc. are included in **D4.1. Implementation of R17: non ICT based Innovative Social Actions (Social Action Plan).**

As detailed in D4.1, new updates of D4.1 will add, to the current information about all the non ICT Social Actions, the integration of the use of the IT tools developed during the project, in order to have only one document with a deep description of the environmental education actions in terms of systemic and comprehensive pilot's strategy on social actions.

ICT based educational tools are already described in their own deliverables: Teaching Units (Deliverable D4.3-D4.4), Serious Games (Deliverable D4.5-D4.9) and Apps (Deliverable D4.11-D4.12). Citizen Science activities (Deliverable D4.10) are also part of the IT based tools carried out to co-create innovative eco-design solutions.

2 General description of the ICT based tools

2.1 Description of the ICT based tools

The following table includes a short description of the ICT based educational tools that are included in this report:

Type	Name	Description
Apps	Food App (R5)	<p>The FoodApp is an application where food waste generators can donate their surpluses to people who pick it up and reuse it. The app will be available for iOS and Android devices.</p> <p>Users could play two different roles using this app:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - donors, that publish surpluses and - donees, that browse and request surpluses <p>The main functionality of the app is to allow donors and donees to carry out the transaction of food. Some information to avoid food wastage will be given by the App indeed.</p>
	Local Trade App (R6)	<p>The LocalTradeApp is a centralized repository of information about the municipal system that rewards ecological good practices and foster local trade. It will be a part of the Citizen App.</p> <p>Users can browse commerces in several ways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They can use a map to get a general idea of the ecological conscience of local commerce or to get the closer one that fits a given criteria. - Businesses can also be found by good practices. Users can browse these practices through categories to get a given one?
	Citizens App (R7)	<p>The CitizenApp is an application that provides citizens with information related to the waste collection system</p> <p>The app will be available for iOS and Android devices.</p> <p>Through this app, Municipal Administrations will grant access to the citizens to several indicators related to the waste management system. There will be a collection of contents (both static and dynamic) that our curators will administrate through a backend, or that will be precalculated in? a gateway from different sources of information.</p> <p>The app will be structured in some sections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipal information - Sorting information - News about prevention campaign and social actions - Incidences - Personal information <p>When a citizen enters into the app, a main menu is presented to choose the desired information.</p> <p>Almost all the information will be available for anonymous users. Although, user must be logged to visit “Incidences” and “Personal information” sections.</p>

<p>Learning Materials (R8)</p>	<p>DP1 Prevention and reuse</p>	<p>After the concert. Detective game. There is a big party at the village. You went down to the main square to participate in a theatre workshop that is organized in this time period. When you arrive you find a lot of "garbage". The workshop has been canceled. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case. METHODOLOGY: - Analyze the "crime" scenario. - Collect clues and look for the guilty ones. - Identify how it could have been avoided. - Look for solutions. - Communicate what has happened to other citizens. CONTENTS: - Basic terminology on waste and its management. - Prevention measures in the generation of MSW. - Identification and classification of waste. - Identification of necessary resources for the management of MSW. - Appropriate waste management for the generation of quality resources - People as agents of change.</p>
	<p>DP2 Source separation and recycling</p>	<p>Looking for the Treasure. You have just arrived at your class-room and realized that the trash can is overturned and there are remains of food on the floor. It seems that an animal has entered in the class. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and look for it. METHODOLOGY: - Analyze the scenario. - Collect tracks. - Identify how it could have been avoided. - Look for solutions. - Share/Communicate what happened. CONTENTS: 1. Being able to search and correctly recognize accumulated resources in the classroom or school. 2. Identifying people as the origin of the generation and management of MSW. 3. Acquiring the necessary knowledge for the correct identification and classification of MSW at the origin, as a first step for further good quality recycling. 4. Internalize the concept of prioritization reducing, reusing and recycling. 5. Developing the capacity to analyze and extract data from generated / managed waste in an approximate manner. 6. Developing the analysis capacity of analyze in order to identify the necessary resources for the t management of MSW in your city. 7. Being able to create ideas, search, present and identify preventive measures for waste reduction 8. Being able to identify the value of the resources generated in the classroom</p>

DP3 Home compost/ Food waste	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around Home compost & foodwaste in general
DP4 Product Life Cycle	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around Life Cycle of products and services
DP5 Waste Tax	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around waste tax and PAYT
DP6 Monitoring of waste generation	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to help in waste monitoring at different levels (school, house, city, etc.)
MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME	<p>The aim of this mobile game is to develop a tool for monitoring the waste/resource generation and the time evolution in a funny an easy way. Most of the monitoring tools that we have found in the market are adult-oriented and the usability, aesthetic and functionalities are not adapted to W4T target group. This mobile game will allow to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Record the waste generation in an easy way. - Adapt the data collection to personal, family, school or other collective or spaces. - Visualize an historical timeline evolution. - Identify changes related to specific improvement actions. - Give recommendations based in a prevention and low waste generation model. - Compare the municipality waste generation figures with external data from other towns, countries or schools accessible via W4T platform. - Engage the user via gamification methodology
MG2. SUNFLOWER	<p>Making a good quality compost is the key for having a good crop. Discover the secrets of the best compost and keep your sunflower alive. Reach the best temperature, humidity and feed the microorganisms and organisms with the best organic waste so that they help you achieving your goals.</p> <p>Combine your compost management dashboard with AR technology for better visualizing the evolution of your plant. This game will allow to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use some real data like brightness (from the mobile camera), or temperature and humidity (if there is connection to the net) for encouraging the movement of people to achieve better results. - choose which resources to be used for your compost. - Manage from 1 to 3 composters for experimenting with different resources to make the best material. - Discover microorganism and organism involve in each phase of the composting. - Share and showing data via W4T platform

	<p>MG3. TREASURE MACHINE</p>	<p>Identifying the value of waste is the key point for moving its definition from waste to resource. This game will allow to better understand the importance of a good sorting at the origin and will improve the way the society looks to resource management systems. The resources machine main objective is to show the real value of "waste".</p> <p>In this game the user must identify the value of the resources that have arrived to the "waste" sorting machine. For each element identified, some elements to improve the sorting in origin are won. In consequence, the machine will work better and will be easier to identify value objects. Finally, a machine full of treasures will be developed and will come back to society with a new life.</p> <p>This game will allow to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the value of resources - Identify good practices to improve the sorting in origin. - Have fun learning about product life cycle and circular economy. - Share and show data via W4T platform.
	<p>MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION</p>	<p>A game to deal in real-time with waste generation and management.</p> <p>The game will have from 5 to 10 general missions that everybody can develop at his own house, town, city, school or Business place. The games will be based on innovative technologies such as AR, QR or image recognition.</p> <p>The purpose is to search and record all the waste management tools that you can find in your school and identify what kind of resource is sorted there. How much waste is generated in each space?</p> <p>In which spaces the resources are generated? Find and collect all of them.</p> <p>Can you identify green spaces or 0 waste spaces? Search and collect them.</p> <p>This game will allow to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor the spaces and tools for resource management. - Identify green or 0 waste spaces - Use the AR and image recognition for engaging people. - Share and show data via W4T platform.
<p>Serious Games</p>	<p>Ways2Sort (R9)</p>	<p>Will incorporate data from municipalities in order to teach waste sorting strategies that are relevant to the location. The basic mechanic of the game consists of waste items appearing in the screen which needs to be sorted into the correct recycling bin. The maximum number of conveyor belts on one screen will be five</p>
	<p>Ecodesign game (R10)</p>	<p>A half-explorative puzzle game where a player designs and produces different versions of a product according to different market demands. The goal of the game is to communicate how changing the design, processes and materials in manufacturing a product, however small, will have an impact. Main focus of the game should be on problem-solving in designing, producing, logistics, use and end of life stages.</p>

	<p>Virtual City game (R12)</p>	<p>A turn-based strategy game for 4 players that takes place on a hexagonal map. Based on the concept of circular economy, players take on a role as one of the stages of the circular economy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Producer • Supplier • Community • Disposer <p>Players have to collaborate on a global eco-score as the players will all fail if that goes below 0. In addition to that each player also have their own finances and research to manage.</p> <p>The learning goal is to communicate the principles of circular economy, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The lifecycle of product and the interdependency of different actors in this cycle • Identifying four main actors and their respective roles in the circle • The benefits of having a circular economy in respect to environmental concerns and sustainability and resource management • Critical thinking about mainstream production economies compared to circular economies • The crucial role of waste and recycling <p>The game will be used as a dialogue tool where we imagine 4 players to be physically present in the same room in order to maximise discussion, reflexion and learning outcomes.</p>
	<p>Planning Game (R11)</p>	<p>A turn based strategy game, where players have to build the waste management strategy for their own town. Collection method, number and positioning of the containers, collection routes, treatment plants, taxes, social awareness campaigns, etc. should be defined in order to satisfy the services.</p> <p>Different scenarios will be provided where the player should try to give to the citizens the best service with less impact in a pre-fixed number of turns. During the stages “things happen” (randomly and non randomly) that change the external conditions of the scenario (like an invasion of English tourists in summer, Christmas holidays, or even a tifon) and the gamers should quickly respond.</p> <p>The objective is twofold:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • on the one hand, to teach citizens the complexity of a waste management strategy. • on the other hand, to be the cornerstone of the citizen science actions latter on in the project.
<p>Other</p>	<p>Littering App</p>	<p>App to map littering "hot points". Developed by ARS for other project, will be used in Seveso for littering monitoring.</p>

Table 1 Description of ICT based educational tools

2.2 Main characteristics of the Social Action Plan

2.2.1 Integration of IT tools

Fig. 1. Social Action Plan scheme

The Waste 4 Think Social Actions Plan is innovative in many senses:

1. the actions are aimed to achieve a **high and active interaction with the target groups** involved, through participation groups, citizens science actions, demonstrative activities and others;
2. the **monitoring** of these social actions, both in qualitative and quantitative way, to assure not only the replicability but that lessons learnt are recorded and could be used to be more efficient and effective in the future
3. also a mid-term planning has been done for each strategy line and synergies among them, **integrating the ecosolutions** that are being developed during the project, especially the “educational ones” but also the PAYT system or others;

In all of these focuses, IT tools will help to achieve the expected results.

Fig. 2. *Integration of different tools to achieve results. “Jigsaw” simile.*

One of the key points of Waste4Think project is the integration of ecosolutions along all the waste management chain. This is especially important to achieve a high and positive social impact. In order to effectively improve the results of prevention and separate collection, it is mandatory to have both a high quality of the service and high participation of the different stakeholders. But it is a must to introduce in a coordinated way all the different instruments that allows the achievement of the objectives. We can make a parallelism with a jigsaw, you need to put all pieces to see the final image, in this case, to achieve prevention and separate collection. And necessary pieces are, educational, of course, but also a good technical scheme and correct operative; to have a suitable legal framework; and also to add the correct economical tools to push waste habits to the correct direction (for example, PAYT schemes).

In Waste4Think we are integrating this kind of solutions, to demonstrate how to achieve effective prevention and separate collection while environmental impacts due to waste management services are reduced. In this sense, the integration of the Technologies of Information and Communication has a special relevance.

2.2.2 Success factors to achieve high separate collection rates. Interaction with SA Plan

There are a number of factors that lead towards the achievement of the goals we are facing in the project, with respect the use of IT tools next factors can be highlighted:

- 1. Co-responsibility of the system users**
 - 1.1. *Loss of anonymity*
 - 1.2. *Awareness and generation of critical thinking*
 - 1.3. *Economic consciousness*

2. Equality of conditions or positive discrimination for separate collection versus residual/mixed fraction.

2.1. *Frequencies of collection // bin access*

2.2. *Proximity*

Regarding point 1.1, IT based tools used for awareness purposes can follow a flow chart like this:

Fig. 3. Utilities of USER identification

To enhance co-responsibility, one of the main factors to achieve is the loss of anonymity in waste management. First step is to have an USER ID (as in Seveso, Cascais and Zamudio pilot) and read this ID each time the user interact with the collection system (or at least some fractions considered as “indicators” of the behavior of the users, especially residual fraction).

This is usually perceived by users (domestic or commercial) as “control” in somehow of “big brother” effect that need to be explained and justified very well. The finality of the system is not the control itself, it is the collection operative improvement, the final application of some benefits in a more fair tax system in terms of money or other savings, other kind of benefits taking into account the user habits on separate collection, the personalization of messages to the users, etc.

In any case, this monitoring information could (and must be used) also for a better knowledge of the users themselves:

Fig. 4. Patterns information for awareness raising purposes

As mentioned, this information, this use patterns, could be used for awareness purposes. Especially for direct, constant and more flexible and interactive communication. To help with this “interaction” some tools could be developed, more or less complex. Waste4Think is developing the Citizens App to help users to know their habits, how they generate and throw their waste (or resources), to interact with the municipality also reporting incidences or doubts, to inform about the cost of waste management collective and individual cost, etc. The objective is not only to change habits, is to create critical thinking and empower citizens.

Fig. 5. Image of the Citizens App design proposal

Regarding how to work on the “economic” consciousness, there are so many ways that smart technologies can help us (see D5.1 and D5.3). In any case, although economic issues are usually mentioned by citizens as a change factor, some projects have demonstrated that it is not enough (or changes are not so big) if it is not linked to other instruments, specially, waste collection system configuration and awareness raising.

Fig. 6. Economical tools

3 Definition of Target Groups for the Social Actions

Actions

To develop the forecast of use and integration of the different tools in the Social Actions and Strategies, the target groups and availability of each one have been defined previously:

Type of ICT Tool	Name	Short description	Target	Availability forecast
Apps	Food App	App to promote donation of food	General citizens + Food retailers+ NGOs	Final nov-18
	Local Trade App	App to foster local trade and sustainable consumption	General citizens + Commercial activities	Final oct 18
	Citizens App	App to provide citizens with information related to the waste collection system	General citizens. High level knowledge?	Final oct 18
Learning Materials	DP1 Prevention and reuse	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around prevention and reuse	6-16 y	Already available version 1
	DP2 Source separation and recycling	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around source separation & recycling	6-16 y	Already available version 1
	DP3 Home compost/Food waste	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around Home compost & foodwaste in general	6-16 y	Oct-18
	DP4 Product Life Cycle	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around Life Cycle of products and services	6-16 y	nNov-18
	DP5 Waste Tax	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around waste tax and PAYT	6-16 y	Oct-18
	DP6 Monitoring of waste generation	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to help in waste monitoring at different levels (school, house, city...)	6-16 y	Nov-18
	MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME	Tool for monitoring the waste/resource generation and the time evolution in a funny an easy way.	6-16 y	Nov-18

Type of ICT	Name	Short description	Target	Availability
	MG2. SUNFLOWER	Discover the secrets of the best compost and keep your sunflower alive.	6-16 y	Oct-18
	MG3. TREASURE MACHINE	Show the real value of "waste". Aimed at explain circular economy in an easy way.	6-16 y	Nov-18
	MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION	"Gimkana game" with specific challenges adapted to each pilot	6-16 y	Nov-18
Serious Games	Ways2Sort	Educate mainly young children on the importance of sorting waste and how to sort waste.	General, since 6 y children	Sep-18
	Ecodesign game	A half-explorative puzzle game where a player designs and produces different versions of a product according to different market demands.	University students	Sep-18
	Virtual City game	Game to communicate the principles of circular economy	General citizens. High level knowledge?	Feb-19
	Planning Game	Players have to build the waste management strategy for their own town	General citizens	Dec-18
Other	Littering App	App to map littering "hot points". Developed by ARS for other project, will be used in Seveso for littering monitoring.	Volunteers	Already available for SEVESO

Table 2 Target group and availability forecast

4 Methodology to define the integration of the ICT based tools

To help the pilots to define how to use the available ICT based tools, the pilots leaders had been provided with the updated version of D4.1 and all the previous information about the ecosolutions R5-R12. With this information they have had to fulfill a matrix as the one in Table 4 and describe the use of the new tool for the selected Social Action/s, in a small table, as the one in Table 3.

This is the information they received:

1. Objective

Detect and describe the use of the ICT solutions in the Environmental Education Program. The idea is to use them during the implementation of the FORESEEN actions or detect NEW opportunities to develop new social actions around them.

2. How to proceed

1 Each pilot has a dedicated Excel sheet. In each one you can find a matrix (Table 4) with main information of the different ecosolutions developed by Waste4Think. You can add others you have in your municipality if you want (CityPoints in Cascais, Littering App in Seveso...).

2 Please, check in which social action you can use one or more of the ecosolutions. You can add new columns if you detect a new opportunity and a new action could be added to the current planning. Put the corresponding cell in color (you can find an invented example in the Zamudio sheet).

3 If you need more information about the ecosolutions to decide, you can find a deeper description here ([Table 1](#))

4 Please, add in a word document a short description of the foreseen use of each ecosolution in each social action following the next template (one description x social action, can include the use of 1 or more ecosolutions)

Social Action code:
Ecosolution/s used:
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Calendar

Table 3 Template to describe the use of the ICT based tool in the Social Action Plan.

The completed matrix fulfilled by each pilot is presented in chapters 6 to 9. Besides, the way that each ecosolution will be integrated in the selected social action, according to the provided template is also presented for each pilot.

Preparation of D4.2 Integration of the ICT ecosolutions to the Environmental Educational Program

Type of ICT Tool	Name	Short description (see further description of the ICT ecosolutions)	Target	Disponibility forecast	Z1. General campaign					Z2. Schools campaign and activities				
					Z1.1 General presentations	Z1.2 Participation workshop	Z1.3 Citizens science actions	Z1.4 "Non bota zer" campaign	Z1.5 Summer camp	Z2.1 Learning materials aplication	Z2.2 Self-composting	Z2.3 Light packkaging prevention campaign	Z2.4 Improve separate collection and prevention	Z2.5 Workshops
Apps	Food App	App to promote donation of food	General citizens + Food retailers+ NGOs	final nov 18										
	Local Trade App	App to foster local trade and sustainable consumption	General citizens + Commercial activities	final oct 18										
	Citizens App	App to provide citizens with information related to the waste collection system	General citizens. High level knowledge?	final oct 18										
Learning Materials	DP1 Prevention and reuse	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around prevention and reuse	6-16 y	already available version 1										
	DP2 Source separation and recycling	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around source separation & recycling	6-16 y	already available version 1										
	DP3 Home compost/Food waste	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around Home compost & foodwaste in general	6-16 y	oct-18										
	DP4 Product Life Cycle	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around Life Cycle of products and services	6-16 y	nov-18										
	DP5 Waste Tax	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around waste tax and PAYT	6-16 y	oct-18										
	DP6 Monitoring of waste generation	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to help in waste monitoring at different levels (school, house, city...)	6-16 y	nov-18										

5 Integration of ICT tools in Zamudio's Social Action Plan

5.2 Social actions and use of ICT based tools

In general terms, during all the actions and activities in Zamudio the games and apps will be explained to the citizens and how to use/play (Z1.1 and Z1.2). Z1.5, Z4.2 and 4.3 have been deployed before the tools are available, so it has not been possible to use them.

Social Action code:	Z1.3 Citizens Science
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Trade App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	In the workshop it will be explained to people how the app works so they can use it on their own during a citizens science activity.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	Some smart phones with downloaded applications and a projector to explain how to play.
Calendar	December 2019

Social Action code:	Z1.4 "Non bota zer" campaign
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizens App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	They will distribute the dictionaries of "zer bota non" and at the same time it will be informed about the existence of an app to be able to know to what fraction it is necessary to throw everything.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	
Calendar	February 2019

Social Action code:
Z2.1 Learning materials application
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP1 Prevention and reuse • DP2 Source separation and recycling • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • DP4 Product Life Cycle • DP5 Waste Tax • DP6 Monitoring of waste generation • MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME • MG2. SUNFLOWER • MG3. TREASURE MACHINE • Ways2Sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Schools will use these learning materials in class.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers
Calendar
January 2019

Social Action code:
Z2.2 Self-composting
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • MG2. SUNFLOWER
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Schools will use these learning materials at school to improve the compost process.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers.
Calendar
January 2019

Social Action code:
Z2.3 Light packaging prevention campaign
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP1 Prevention and reuse • DP6 Monitoring of waste generation • MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME • MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION • Ways2Sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Schools will use these learning materials at school to try reducing light packaging.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers
Calendar
February 2019

Social Action code:
Z2.4 Improve separate collection and prevention
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP2 Source separation and recycling • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • DP5 Waste Tax • DP6 Monitoring of waste generation • MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME • MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION • Ways2Sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Schools will use these learning materials at school to try improving separate collection.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers
Calendar
February 2019

Social Action code:
Z3.1 General campaign
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

Hold a meeting with NGOs and food retailers to explain how the app works and so that it can start to be put into operation.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphones.
Calendar
Depends on when is the app ready to use.

Social Action code:
Z3.2 Creative cooking course
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App • DP1 Prevention and reuse
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Prepare a meal with donated food and explain to people through which app the food has been obtained and how it works.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphones, place to cook and donated food.
Calendar
May 2019

Social Action code:
Z3.3 Food App
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The best form to understand through creative cooking course and other promotional actions
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Calendar

Social Action code:
Z4.1 Diagnosis
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Trade App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

Meeting to see through the app how everything is working and discuss how to improve.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphones.
Calendar
June 2019

Social Action code:
Z4.4 Local Trade App campaign
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Trade App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Meeting between the town hall and the merchants to discuss how to get the most out of the app and explain to the merchants how it works.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphones.
Calendar
December 2019

Social Action code:
Z5.1 Community composting plant
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DP3 Home compost/Food waste MG2. SUNFLOWER
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
An on-site visit to the community composting plant with the schools so that the students can see how the composting plant is working after using the learning materials at the school.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers.
Calendar
January 2019

Social Action code:
Z6.1 General informations
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP5 Waste Tax • Virtual City game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Put a tent in the center of the town for citizens to approach and the street educator can make a demonstration of how the apps work.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphone and tent.
Calendar
March 2019

Social Action code:
Z8.1 Day festivals
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ways2Sort • Virtual City game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Put a tent where the party is held so that citizens can get closer and the street educator can make a demonstration of how the apps work.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphone and tent.
Calendar
May 2019

Social Action code:
Z8.2 Popular meals
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ways2Sort • Ecodesign game • Virtual City game • Planning Game

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Put a tent where the party is held so that citizens can get closer and the street educator can make a demonstration of how the apps work.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphone and tent.
Calendar
When a popular meal is celebrated.

Social Action code:	LAN party
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecodesign game • Virtual City game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	Put a tent where the party is held so that citizens can get closer and the street educator can make a demonstration of how the apps work.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	Smartphone and tent.
Calendar	It has not yet been published when the LAN party is going to be held.

6 Integration of ICT tools in Halandri's Social Action Plan

6.1 Matrix

Preparation of D4.2 Integration of the ICT ecosolutions to the Environmental Educational Program

Type of ICT Tool	Name	Short description (see further description of the ICT ecosolutions)	Target	Disponibility forecast	H1. Educational centers activities		H2. Actions at Technical University		H3. Food separate collection and treatment		H4 Commercial activities campaign	
					H1.1 Vocational school	H1.2 Gymnasium	H2.2 Use of the Ecodesign game	H3.3 Feedback to the citizens	H3.4 Extension of the new collection	H4.1 citizens science	H4.2 Promotion of best consumption habits	
Apps	Food App	App to promote donation of food	General citizens + Food retailers+ NGOs	pending to define								
	Local Trade App	App to foster local trade and sustainable consumption	General citizens + Commercial activities	final oct 18								
	Citizens App	App to provide citizens with information related to the waste collection system	General citizens. High level knowledge?	final oct 18								
Learning Materials	DP1 Prevention and reuse	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with	6-16 y	Already available version 1								
	DP2 Source separation and recycling	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around source separation & recycling	6-16 y	Already available version 1								
	DP3 Home compost/Food waste	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around Home compost & foodwaste in general	6-16 y	oct-18								
	DP4 Product Life Cycle	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around Life Cycle of products and services	6-16 y	nov-18								
	DP5 Waste Tax	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around waste tax and PAYT	6-16 y	oct-18								
	DP6 Monitoring of waste generation	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim of help in waste monitoring at different levels (school, house, city...)	6-16 y	nov-18								
	MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME	Tool for monitoring the waste/resource generation and the time evolution in a funny an easy way.	6-16 y	nov-18								
	MG2. SUNFLOWER	Discover the secrets of the best compost and keep your sunflower alive.	6-16 y	oct-18								
	MG3. TREASURE MACHINE	Show the real value of "waste". Aimed at explain circular economy in an easy way.	6-16 y	nov-18								
	MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION	"Gimkana game" with specific challenges adapted to each pilot	6-16 y	nov-18								
Serious Games	Ways2Sort	Educate mainly young children on the	General, since 6 y children	sep-18								
	Ecodesign game	A half-explorative puzzle game where a player designs and produces different versions of a product according to different market demands.	University students	sep-18								
	Virtual City game	Game to communicate the principles of circular economy	General citizens. High level knowledge?	feb-19								
	Planning Game	Players have to build the waste management strategy for their own town	General citizens	dic-18								

Fig. 8. Matrix Social Actions vs ICT tools (R5-R12) in Halandri

6.2 Social actions and use of ICT based tools

Social Action code
H1.1 Vocational School
Ecosolution/s used:
DP1 Prevention and reuse DP2 Source separation and recycling DP3 Home compost/Food waste DP4 Product Life Cycle DP6 Monitoring of waste generation MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME MG2. SUNFLOWER MG3. TREASURE MACHINE MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The Ecosolutions will be used in the context of the Environmental Program and the Technology Program of the school (non-typical education), with a specific focus on waste management lessons in the 4 specific thematic areas (source separation and recycling, prevention/reuse, Home compost/food waste, monitoring of waste generation) that have been identified since March '17. The games will be used to support core actions based on DP1-6 and also actions which the schools themselves develop based on the guidelines provided by the Waste4Think team. Where available, data from the apps will be analyzed to assess the impact of the program to the students.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Manuals for the apps, possible need for PCs and/or tablets
Calendar
Educational actions in schools begin on mid-October at the earliest (depending on the school). As soon as the ecosolutions become available, they will be adapted and incorporated in the program.

Social Action code
H1.2 Gymnasium
Ecosolution/s used:
DP1 Prevention and reuse DP2 Source separation and recycling DP3 Home compost/Food waste DP4 Product Life Cycle DP6 Monitoring of waste generation MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME MG2. SUNFLOWER

MG3. TREASURE MACHINE MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION Ways2sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The Ecosolutions will be used in the context of the Environmental Program of the school (non-typical education), with a specific focus on waste management lessons in the 4 specific thematic areas (source separation and recycling, prevention/reuse, Home compost/food waste, monitoring of waste generation) that have been identified since March '17. The games will be used to support core actions based on DP1-6 and also actions which the schools themselves develop based on the guidelines provided by the Waste4Think team. Where available, data from the apps will be analyzed to assess the impact of the program to the students.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Manuals for the apps, possible need for PCs and/or tablets
Calendar
Educational actions in schools begin on mid-October at the earliest (depending on the school). As soon as the ecosolutions become available, they will be adapted and incorporated in the program.

Social Action code
H2.2 Use of the eco-design game
Ecosolution/s used:
Eco-design game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
During a series of lectures students will be asked to play the developed eco-design game, following its instructions.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Eco-design game
Calendar
Use of eco-design game will take place during the winter semester 2019 (September 2018-February 2019).

Social Action code
H3.3 Feedback to the citizens & H3.4 Extension of the new collection
Ecosolution/s used:
Local Trade App Citizens App Virtual City Game Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The citizen app will find the heaviest use, since it is expected to provide information on the new system, and also collect feedback which can be extremely important in the rolling out phase of the introduction of the brown bin in a whole municipal section. The Local Trade App will provide positive publicity to local enterprises which use effectively the new system and so act as an incentive, especially in the center of the municipality where heavy commercial activity may be found. The two games will: 1) raise awareness of the benefits of the new system and so ease the adoption from citizens/players and 2) provide data (scenario created by players) which can be used to optimize the new system.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Calendar
The extension of the new collection system (introduction of the brown bin) will start (tentatively) in late October/early November 2018 in a section which corresponds to approximately 10% of the population of Halandri. Extension to the rest of the municipality will take place accordingly, based on lessons learned from this initial extension to the general public. All of the apps will be introduced to the target groups as soon as possible.

Social Action code
H4.1 Citizens Science
Ecosolution/s used:
Local Trade App Virtual City Game Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The primary ecosolution is the Local Trade App. The results of the surveys from the citizen science action will be introduced in the Local Trade App to promote good habits adopted by local enterprises. The two games can be used by the Citizen Science group to further advance their knowledge in the inner workings of waste management and thus create a solid core in the society of the municipality with extensive understanding of waste management and its implications.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed

Possibly tablets or computers, printed manual of the apps
Calendar
The citizen science group is already working. The apps will be introduced to the group as soon as they are available.

Social Action code
H4.2 Promotion of best consumption habits
Ecosolution/s used:
Food App Local Trade App Virtual City Game Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The Local Trade App will raise awareness of good consumption habits, by indicating and promoting in a positive way good trade practices, thus attempting to create a market for enterprises which adopt good habits (good trading habits are also mirrored to a great extent to good consumer habits). The two games will raise awareness on the general effect these habits have, both to the waste management system of the municipality and to the city as a whole.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Promotional materials for the apps, printed manuals, possibly CDs to be distributed at public places
Calendar
The ecosolutions should be introduced to their target groups as soon as they become available.

7 Integration of ICT tools in Seveso's Social Action Plan

7.1 Matrix

Type of ICT Tool	Name	Short description (see further description of the ICT ecosolutions)	Target	Disponibility forecast	SE1. Citizens funny sensitization				SE2. Virtuous households		SE3. Ecoevents	SE4. PAYT	
					SE1.1 Dinner or Lunch with waste	SE1.2 Sensitization activity in public spaces	SE1.4 Sensitization in schools	SE1.6 sensitization in private courtyards	SE2.2 Trainings monitoring period	SE2.4 - second stage: VH focusing on waste prevention	SE3.2 Celebration of the Ecoevents	SE4.1 Monitoring, tax calculation & preparation	SE4.4 Littering monitoring
Apps	Food App	App to promote donation of food	General citizens + Food retailers + NGOs	pending to define									
	Local Trade App	App to foster local trade and sustainable consumption	General citizens + Commercial activities	final oct 18									
	Citizens App	App to provide citizens with information related to the waste collection system	General citizens. High level knowledge?	final oct 18									
Serious Games	Ways2Sort	Educate mainly young children on the importance of sorting waste and how to sort waste.	General, since 6 y children	sep-18									
	Ecodesign game	A half-explorative puzzle game where a player designs and produces different versions of a product according to different market demands.	Universitary students	sep-18									
	Virtual City game	Game to communicate the principles of circular economy	General citizens. High level knowledge?	feb-19									
	Planning Game	Players have to build the waste management strategy for their own town	General citizens	dic-18									
Other	Littering App	App to map littering "hot points". Developed by ARS for other project, will be used in Seveso for littering monitoring.	?	Already available for SEVESO									
	Plogging tool	Tool for plogging (runners monitoring and collecting abandoned waste)	Runners	December 2018									

Fig. 9. Matrix Social Actions vs ICT tools (R5-R12) in Seveso

7.2 Social Actions and integration of ICT tools

Social Action code:	SE 1.1 – dinners with waste
Ecoslution/s used:	Citizen’s App, Ways2Sort, Ecodesign game, Virtual city game, Planning game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	The citizen app and the serious games will be explained to citizens during dinners; the most complex serious games will be addressed to more sensitized people. Citizen app will be useful to show real time individual generation of waste Ways2Sort will be tested in a collective way to see where to throw difficult items and maybe to set up a competition
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	The Citizen App must be able to retrieve data about residual waste individual generation, through Wintarif / Fiware
Calendar	A dinner with waste is foreseen for 21 st September 2018. Others, when the SG are ready and after the implementation of the Citizen App / integration with Fiware data. Mid 2019?

Social Action code:	SE1.2 Sensitization activity in public spaces
Ecoslution/s used:	Citizen’s App, Ways2Sort, Ecodesign game, Virtual city game, Planning game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	In public spaces with general target (markets, streets, public events) a demo of Ways2Sort and the Citizen App will be presented. For more complex SG, specific laboratories will be organized targeting high school and university students at FLA (Fondazione Lombardia per l’Ambiente).
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	The Citizen App must be able to retrieve data about residual waste individual generation, through Wintarif / Fiware Roll up with QR code and screenshots of Citizen App and Ways2Sort Cooperation between Innova21 and FLA to manage laboratories on SG.
Calendar	After the implementation of the Citizen App / integration with Fiware data. Mid 2019? Laboratories with FLA: as soon as SG are ready.

Social Action code:	SE1.4 sensitization in schools
Ecoslution/s used:	Ways2Sort, ecodesign game, virtual city game, planning game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	Students in primary schools will be shown how to use Ways2sort. Students in secondary schools will also see other SG (serious games) and will develop small projects and researches on it. A tablet will be used to show them, linked to the class beamer.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	Agreement with teachers. Beta / Final version of the Serious Games.
Calendar	As soon as the beta is available.

Social Action code:	SE1.6 sensitization in private courtyards
Ecoslution/s used:	Citizen's App, Ways2Sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	Ways2Sort will be used in private courtyard events. The citizen app will be explained. Ways2Sort will be used to see how people behave after responding to a questionnaire on separation of difficult items.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	The Citizen App must be able to retrieve data about residual waste individual generation, through Wintarif / Fiware Roll up with QR code and screenshots of Citizen App and Ways2Sort
Calendar	After the implementation of the Citizen App / integration with Fiware data. Mid 2019? Just Ways2Sort: public events to be organized in spring/summer 2019

Social Action code:	SE2.2 – Virtuous Households – training and monitoring period and S2.4 – virtuous households second stage (focus on waste prevention)
Ecoslution/s used:	Ways2Sort, ecodesign game, local trade app
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	The second round of the VH action (foreseen in spring 2019) will be focusing on waste prevention. 10 families will be monitored to check their waste reduction, and the 2 ecosolutions (W2S and ecodesign) will contribute to their training. Local trade app may be used to invite people to go to local shops where they can use reusable containers etc.

New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The Ecodesign game should be effective enough to foster good waste prevention habits. Local trade app should be translated in Italian
Calendar
Spring 2019

Social Action code:
SE3.2 – Celebration of ecoevents
Ecosolution/s used:
Ways2Sort, ecodesign game, Virtual City Game, Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
In a specific ecoevent in summer 2019 (maybe AMALO event), a “serious game” session could be organized, maybe in the afternoon before the dinner, to explain the games and sensitize participants, mostly students.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Final version of the SG.
Calendar
June 2019

Social Action code:
SE 4.1 – PAYT monitoring – tax calculation
Ecosolution/s used:
Citizen’s App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The citizen app will be used by citizens to see real time individual generation of waste
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The Citizen App must be able to retrieve data about residual waste individual generation, through Wintarif / Fiware
Calendar
As soon as possible, after the implementation of the Citizen App / integration with Fiware data. Mid 2019?

Social Action code:	SE 4.4 – PAYT - littering monitoring
Ecoslution/s used:	App “Puliamo il Mondo” prepared by ARS and used by Legambiente. Plogging monitoring tool
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	Local activists of Legambiente will use the app by ARS to monitor the spots where waste is abandoned and littering occurs The local Marathon Running Club will be involved to monitor constantly a specific path in the city / park to count how many abandoned waste bags are present and for plogging activities (running collecting waste), using specific tools which integrates WhatsApp and google doc
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	The plogging tool will be developed by ARS to integrate WhatsApp messages with a database to store info about bags and pictures.
Calendar	Starting December 2018

8 Integration of ICT tools in Cascais's Social Action Plan

8.1 Matrix

Type of ICT Tool	Name	Short description (see further description of the ICT ecosolutions)	Target	Disponibility forecast	C1. ID/PAY containers system					C2. Tourist engagement		C3. Waste4Think schools		
					C1.1 Preparation activities	C1.2 Implementation campaign- consominium meetings	C1.3 Gammification - award system	C1.4 Promotion of W4T Apps and games	C1.5 Feedback	C2.1 Information to Landlords	C2.2 Dedicated campaign	C3.1 Learning materials use	C3.2 Serious games	C3.3 EMAC own activities
Apps	Food App	App to promote donation of food	General citizens + Food retailers+ NGOs	pending to define										
	Local Trade App	App to foster local trade and sustainable consumption	General citizens + Commercial activities	final oct 18										
	Citizens App	App to provide citizens with information related to the waste collection system	General citizens. High level knowledge?	final oct 18										
Learning Materials	DP1 Prevention and reuse	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around prevention and reuse	6-16 y	Already available version 1										
	DP2 Source separation and recycling	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around source separation & recycling	6-16 y	Already available version 1										
	DP3 Home compost/Food waste	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around Home compost & foodwaste in general	6-16 y	oct-18										
	DP4 Product Life Cycle	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around Life Cycle of products and services	6-16 y	nov-18										
	DP5 Waste Tax	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim of increase knowledge around waste tax and PAYT	6-16 y	oct-18										
	DP6 Monitoring of waste generation	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim of help in waste monitoring at different levels (school, house, city...)	6-16 y	nov-18										
	MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME	Tool for monitoring the waste/resource generation and the time evolution in a funny an easy way.	6-16 y	nov-18										
	MG2. SUNFLOWER	Discover the secrets of the best compost and keep your sunflower alive.	6-16 y	oct-18										
	MG3. TREASURE MACHINE	Show the real value of "waste". Aimed at explain circular economy in an easy way.	6-16 y	nov-18										
	MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION	"Gimkana game" with specific challenges adapted to each pilot	6-16 y	nov-18										
Serious Games	Ways2Sort	Educate mainly young children on the importance of sorting waste and how to sort waste.	General, since 6 y children	sep-18										
	Ecodesign game	A half-explorative puzzle game where a player designs and produces different versions of a product according to different market demands.	Universitary students	sep-18										
	Virtual City game	Game to communicate the principles of circular economy	General citizens. High level knowledge?	feb-19										
	Planning Game	Players have to build the waste management strategy for their own town	General citizens	dic-18										
Other	Littering App	App to map littering "hot points". Developed by ARS for other project, will be used in Seveso for littering monitoring.	?	Already available for SEVESO										
(Add others)														

Fig. 10. Matrix Social Actions vs ICT tools (R5-R12) in Cascais

8.2 Social Actions and integration of ICT tools

Social Action code:	C1.1 Preparation Activities
Ecosolution/s used:	No ecosolution used
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	The preparation activities comprise actions in designing posters, leaflets and inquiries at technical level to better understand the process of engaging citizens. This is made within the
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	Flyers, organic waste bags, key holders.
Calendar	April 2018

Social Action code:	C1.2 Implementation campaign-condominium meetings
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP2 Source separation and recycling
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	Meetings with condominiums will be made according to the planned agenda of each building management as we will add the Waste4Think project in their agenda. However, it is noteworthy that the condominium agenda proposal did not work well in the first stages of the participant registration as the participation rate in these meetings is very low and it only occurs every six months.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	Flyers, organic waste bags, key holders.
Calendar	April 2018

Social Action code:	C1.3 Gammification - award system
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP5 Waste Tax • Ecodesign game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	<p>Despite having our own app (Citypoints Cascais) additional tax knowledge is of added value for project management as we can further the knowledge of younger family members and school students.</p> <p>Ecodesign game will help to achieve these goals in a more engaging method (nontax related).</p>
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	Learning materials related to the tools and games
Calendar	January 2019

Social Action code:	C1.4 Promotion of W4T Apps and games
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App • Local Trade App • Citizens App • Ways2Sort • Ecodesign game • Virtual City game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	<p>All games and apps are designed for different ages and target audience. But we believe that these tools can be used simultaneously by different groups of people in both domestic and school context as it will give a family discussion about the subject. It might even help the discussion within different target audiences on management context (EMAC Team and citizens).</p>
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	Only the applications
Calendar	January 2019

Social Action code:	C1.5 Feedback
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens App • DP6 Monitoring of waste generation
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	We hope that both the citizens app and DP6 monitoring will help to share the message about the waste production evolution in the pilot area during the duration of the project as we will share the waste rate and production in our activities.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	The application itself and the related information from the monitoring process.
Calendar	(?) April 2019

Social Action code:	C2.1 Information to Landlords
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens App • DP3 Home compost/Food waste
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	In rented houses, for both tourism short renting and normal renting, we will talk to landlords to promote their awareness on the project, the project's goals and values. For this, we think the applications and food waste are the best items to engage with the people renting the houses as they are easy to use and complete by home users. It will also benefit a cleaner environment in their houses and neighbourhood which, we believe, might add value to their house rental offer.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	The applications, organic waste bags and compost information.
Calendar	(?) April 2019

Social Action code:
C2.2 Dedicated campaign
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local trade App • Citizens App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
For tourist engagement, we seek to give a simple, quick solution to adopt during their short stay to reduce waste production and promote separation. We believe both apps will help with the awareness of these users.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The applications, organic waste bags and compost information.
Calendar
(?) April 2019

Social Action code:
C3.1 Learning materials use
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME • MG2. SUNFLOWER
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The learning materials will be, mostly, used as support for our existing activities from our school activity program within the waste and environment segment. We intend to reach all schools in the surrounding area.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The applications, organic waste bags
Calendar
(?) January 2019

Social Action code:	C3.2 Serious games
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ways2Sort • Ecodesign game • Virtual City Game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	
<p>We intend to use the serious games as relevant awareness tools in direct contacts with participants, in schools and other collective awareness activities. These Serious Games are extremely useful to continuously contact citizens as they can be promoted via internet, school awareness actions and other activities in the pilot area. They add tremendous value to our social activities.</p> <p>As some of these tools are pointed towards adults or general citizens, we intend to reach them by introducing these tools in schools, some older aged students might become familiar with the tools and use it in family context.</p>	
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	
Tool use information (manuals)	
Calendar	
(?) April 2019	

Social Action code:	C3.3 EMAC own activities
Ecosolution/s used:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App • Local Trade App • Citizens App • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • DP5 Waste Tax • Ecodesign game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action	
<p>The apps will be used in school context as additional value to our own activities. We will test their application and start a discussion about waste management in older student classes.</p> <p>The learning materials will also be an addition to some of our activities, as they will enrich the offer of our program. Hence, they will be used outside the pilot area and waste4think project, reaching far more students and communities.</p> <p>The ecodesign game will be used within the context of the NOVA SBE university as they have numerous sustainability related activities and students' groups where this will surely be appreciated.</p>	
New materials, equipment, etc. needed	
Tool use information (manuals)	
Calendar	
(?) April 2019	

9 Calendar of use of ICT based educational tools in the Social action Plan

A Gantt scheme has been developed to detail the calendar of the different strategies and social actions and the use of the ICT based educational tools (R5 to R12).

For each pilot, the calendar of the social actions has been updated and availability of the ecosolutions to be used highlighted in each case.

ID	Name of the ICT tool	Availability forecast
R5	Food App	final november 18
R6	Local Trade App	final oct 18
R7	Citizens App	final oct 18
R8.1	DP1 Prevention and reuse	Already available version 1
R8.2	DP2 Source separation and recycling	Already available version 1
R8.3	DP3 Home compost/Food waste	oct-18
R8.4	DP4 Product Life Cycle	nov-18
R8.5	DP5 Waste Tax	oct-18
R8.6	DP6 Monitoring of waste generation	nov-18
R8.7	MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME	nov-18
R8.8	MG2. SUNFLOWER	oct-18
R8.9	MG3. TREASURE MACHINE	nov-18
R8.10	MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION	nov-18
R9	Ways2Sort	sep-18
R10	Ecodesign game	sep-18
R11	Planning Game	feb-19
R12	Virtual City game	dic-18
External	Littering App, Plogging tool	Already available for SEVESO

Table 5 Guide of Ecosolutions ID, name and availability forecast

Fig. 11. Calendar for Zamudio's Social Action Plan

Fig. 12. Calendar for Seveso's Social Action Plan

10 Monitoring and expected results

Monitoring of these ecosolutions will be done through 3 paths:

- KPI associated to the project as a whole: technical environmental and social indicators to evaluate change of habits reached at the end of the project.
- Specific KPI associated to each Social Action where the use of the ICT based educational tool is used (defined in the Social Action Plan).
- Learning analytics defined for each ecosolution and described in the correspondent deliverable.

For each ecosolution some parameters to be evaluated have been (or are being) defined in order to know the answer to questions like the following:

Pilots would like to learn from the educational materials and the rest of IT tools the following questions:	
Q1	· Do you carry on your own bags and / or shopping cart / container to avoid using single use containers?
Q2	· Which is the impact if you do not separate and classify domestic waste to a greater extent?
Q3	· Do you know where the debris will end up when the truck picks them up?
Q4	· Give your opinion about how easy of use of the citizen card for the deposit of waste is
Q5	· what are the main problems regarding waste management in your locality today?
Q6	· Do you know the rate of waste you pay?
Q7	· Which do you think is the most expensive waste to be managed?
Q8	· Do you think we should all pay the same garbage rate?
Q9	· What amount of cooked food waste do you generate?
Q10	· Do you know about composting and its environmental potential?
Q11	· Do you think recycling is necessary?
Q12	· Do you know the colours of each container?
Q13	· Do you deposit the remains of fruits and vegetables in the brown container or in your auto-compost to make compost?

Table 6 *Some of the questions provided by the pilots to be answered by the use of the ecosolutions*

Some general questions about the users (like gender, age, location) will be asked, also some game metrics will be recorded and it will help to know some interesting patterns and knowledge of the users. Additionally, some pre/post use questions will be introduced in order to have a better background of some interesting issues regarding prevention and separate collection mainly.

11 Documental updating

As explained in the Introduction, for D4.1 an update is foreseen every 6 months, this version will be uploaded and sent to the partners to be reviewed and approved. The next review will include this integration in order to have a complete and real view of the Environmental Educational Program, with both ICT based and non ICT innovative social actions.

12 Annexes

12.1 Update of the SA Plan

Seveso Pilot
<p>SE1 Citizens Sensitization. Funny door to door</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>SE1.1 Dinner or Lunch with waste</i> <i>SE1.2 Sensitization activity in public spaces or existing activities</i> <i>SE1.3 Elderly people house activities</i> <i>SE1.4 Sensitization in schools</i> <i>SE1.5 Sensitization in summer camps with children</i> <i>SE1.6 Sensitization in private courtyards</i> <p>SE2 Campaign “virtuous households”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>SE2.1 Citizens involvement</i> <i>SE2.2 Training and monitoring period</i> <i>SE2.3 Feedback activities</i> <i>SE2.4 -Second stage: VH focusing on waste prevention</i> <p>SE3 Ecoevents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>SE3.1 Preparation of the criteria, tendering and purchasing</i> <i>SE3.2 Celebration and monitoring of the Ecoevents.</i> <p>SE4 PAYT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>SE4.1 Monitoring of the results with RFID bags, tax calculations and preparation of the campaign</i> <i>SE4.2 Implementation campaign.</i> <i>SE4.3 Incidences resolution and feedback to citizens</i> <i>SE4.4 Littering monitoring and dedicated campaign</i>

Seveso Pilot

SE4.5 Other complementary activities

SE5 Promotion campaign of reusable nappies families

SE5.1 Engagement of local stakeholders

SE5.2 Campaign and training development

SE5.3 Feedback to participants and general citizens

SE6. Reusable nappies in a nursery (NEW)

SE6.1 Stakeholders engagement (nursery + washing service)

SE6.2 Implementation

SE6.3 Feedback to participants

Cascais Pilot

C1 ID/PAYT containers system

C1.2 Implementation campaign – condominium meetings

C1.3 Implementation campaign- workshops and DtD visits

C1.4 Gammification-Award system

C1.5 Promotion of the W4T Apps and games

C1.6 Feedback to citizens

C2 Tourist engagement

C2.1 Information to landlords

C2.2 Dedicated campaign

C3 W4T Schools

C3.1 Learning materials (mobile games and STEAM lessons)

C3.2 Sorting game (primary) and Virtual and Planning game (secondary)

C3. 3 EMAC own activities

Zamudio Pilot

Z1 General Campaign

- Z1.1 General presentations and communication*
- Z1.2 Participation workshops*
- Z1.3 Citizens Science action*
- Z1.4 NON BOTA ZER ("Where throw away what") campaign*
- Z1.5 Summer camp*

Z2 Education Centers actions

- Z2.1 Apply learning materials (and gamification) to improve the knowledge of prevention and separate collection*
- Z2.2 Introduce self-composting*
- Z2.3 Promote the reduction of the single use light packaging*
- Z2.4 Improve selective collection and prevention*
- Z2.5 Dedicated workshops in Zamudio Public School*

Z3 Food waste prevention

- Z3.1 General campaign (information point, decalogue about good practices to cut food wastage, etc.)*
- Z3.2 Creative cooking course*
- Z3.3 Food App*
- Z3.4 Food redistribution (Aunar agreement)*

Z4 Commercial activities campaign

- Z4.1 Initial Commercial Activities Diagnosis*
- Z4.2 Tupper campaign*
- Z4.3 Reusable bags campaign*
- Z4.4 Local Trade App Campaign*

Z5 Composting

- Z5.1 Community composting plant*
- Z5.2 Distribution of compost from ZW- Events to participants of balcony flower*

Zamudio Pilot

competition

Z6 PAYT

Z6.1 General information (newsletter, website, other)

Z6.2 Citizens participation process

Z6.3 Commercial activities participation

Z6.4 Industrial activities participation

Z6.5 DtD visits

Z6.6 Dedicated information point

Z7 Zero waste ecosystems

Z7.1 Town Hall pilot

Z7.2 Industries -Hotel

Z8 Ecoevents

Z8.1 "Day" festivals: fairs, demonstrations, running race...

Z8.2 Popular meals

Z8.3 Night festivals : concerts, drinking bars,...

Z9 Miscellanius

Z9.1 Mihiluze Quiz

Z9.2 Halloween - Candle workshop

Z9.3 Promotion of the domestic oil container

LAN party (parallel action)

Halandri Pilot
<p>H1 Educational Centers activities</p> <p><i>H1.1 Vocational School</i></p> <p><i>H1.2 Gymnasium</i></p> <p>H2 Actions at the technical university</p> <p><i>H2.1 Ecodesign modul introduction.</i></p> <p><i>H2.2 Use of the Ecodesign game</i></p> <p>H3 Foodwaste separate collection</p> <p><i>H3.1 Initial seminars and campaign.</i></p> <p><i>H3.2 Starting campaign.</i></p> <p><i>H3.3 Feedback to the citizens.</i></p> <p><i>H3.4 Extension of the new collection.</i></p> <p>H4 Commercial Activities campaign</p> <p><i>H4.1 Citizens science.</i></p> <p><i>H4.2 Promotion of best consumption habits and waste handling in local commerce.</i></p> <p>H5 Nappies collection</p> <p><i>H5.1 Contact with nappies producers to make them participate to the pilot with nappies treatment.</i></p> <p><i>H5.2 Start of the collection & treatment .Virtual operation of the Waste Treatment Unit in relation to typical daily routine of the nursery.</i></p> <p><i>H5.3 Feedback actions to participants</i></p>

Table 7 Pilots Social Actions

12.2 Reviewers comments

Comments from External Reviewers

External Reviewer #1

21/11/2018

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?	x		5
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		5
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		5
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		5
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		5
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		x	4 The Fig. 19 is not in the list of figures
Are the indexes correct?	x		5
Is the written English correct?	x		5
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x		5
Glossary present in the document?	x		5

Jordi Martínez

jmartinez@moba.de

MOBA ISE

Comments from External Reviewers

External Reviewer: Joseba Merino (ZABALA)

DATE: 20th November 2018

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?	x	5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x	5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x	4	Task 4.1 and D4.2 description in the Grant Agreement indicate that a “ Best Practice ” database will be created. They also mention “ Key messages definition ”. If these subjects are addressed in other deliverables (D4.1?), I suggest indicating this in the deliverable.
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x	5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x	5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x	4	The description of the integration of ecosolutions in the SA (especially in Zamudio) could be a little bit more detailed. There are some inconsistencies between the SA identified in each

			<p>pilot matrix (sections 5.1, 6.1 and 7.1) and the ones that are explained in detail (sections 5.2 6.2 and 7.2). It also happens between the matrix and the updated SA plan in the annex.</p> <p>SA integration Plan of Cascais is missing..</p>
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	x	5	
Are the indexes correct?	x	5	
Is the written English correct?	x	5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x	5	
Glossary present in the document?	x	5	

Joseba Merino

jmerino@zabala.es

ZABALA

Comments from External Reviewers

External Reviewer #1

DATE: 23/11/2018

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?	x		5
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		5
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		5
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		5
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		5
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		x	4 Most of the tables are described as figures.
Are the indexes correct?	x		5
Is the written English correct?	x		5
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x		5
Glossary present in the document?	x		4 Glossary and list of abbreviations should be revised (i.e. QR, AR etc.)

Name: Dr. Konstantina Papadopoulou

Email: kpapado@chemeng.ntua.gr

Partner: NTUA

